

A Comparative Kinetic Study of Iridium(III) Catalysis in H_2SO_4 and $HClO_4$ Media in the Cerium(IV) Oxidation of Diacetone Alcohol

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A study of Ir^{III} catalysed oxidation of diacetone alcohol (DAA) by Ce^{IV} in H_2SO_4 and $HClO_4$ media was undertaken to understand the mechanism of catalysis. The change in reactive species of Ce^{IV} in these media produces a marked effect on the relative rates of catalysed and uncatalysed reactions. The catalysis was found to be more pronounced in H_2SO_4 medium. The order in $[Ce^{IV}]$ was found to be unity and that in $[Ir^{III}]$ fractional in both the media studied. The order in [substrate] changed from unity in the uncatalysed reaction to fractional in the catalysed reaction in H_2SO_4 medium. However, in $HClO_4$ medium, the order in [DAA] was found to be fractional both in catalysed as well as uncatalysed reaction. A mechanism involving formation of Ir^{III} -DAA complex in a fast step followed by its reaction with Ce^{IV} in the slow step to give $[Ir^{IV}]$ complex which decomposes to give Ir^{III} and first stage intermediate products is proposed to explain the kinetic data.

VARIOUS metal ions like Ag^+ , Mn^{II} , Cu^{II} , Co^{II} and Ni^{II} have been employed as catalysts in Ce^{IV} oxidation¹. In all these, the catalysis was observed only when the catalyst concentration was $>10^{-3} M$. However, Ru^{III} and Os^{VIII} were found to catalyse Ce^{IV} oxidations in trace amounts^{2,3}, i.e. $10^{-7} M$. In the present work Ir^{III} was found to catalyse the slow reaction between Ce^{IV} and diacetone alcohol (DAA) in trace amounts ($10^{-6} M$). For example, under the condition of $[Ir^{III}] = 5.00 \times 10^{-6} M$, $[Ce^{IV}] = 5.00 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[DAA] = 5.00 \times 10^{-2} M$, $[H^+] = 0.50 M$, at temperature 303 K; the rate constant values (k_{obs}) in the presence of catalyst are 7.68×10^{-4} and 11.7×10^{-4} and in the absence of catalyst 3.83×10^{-5} and $10.2 \times 10^{-5} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ in H_2SO_4 and $HClO_4$ media, respectively. It is known from our earlier work⁴, Ce^{IV} oxidises alcohols in two distinct pathways, direct oxidation and oxidation via complex formation. The first mechanism is usually observed in H_2SO_4 medium and the second in $HClO_4$ and HNO_3 media^{5,6}. In the present investigation, we report the kinetic data of Ir^{III} catalysed oxidation of DAA by Ce^{IV} both in H_2SO_4 and $HClO_4$ media in order to see how the mechanism of catalysis changes with medium.

Experimental

All the chemicals used in this work were of A.R. grade. The solution of Ir^{III} (Johnson Mathey) was standardised by literature procedure⁷. The method of following the rate of reaction was the same as reported earlier⁸. The initial rate method was followed for calculating the order of the reactions. The products of oxidation were identified

as acetone, acetic acid and formic acid by their characteristic tests⁹.

Stoichiometry: The stoichiometry of the reaction was determined by measuring the ceric disappearance by titrimetry and substrate disappearance by measuring the concentration of one of the products, viz. acetone. The concentration of acetone was measured by complexing it with salicylaldehyde in KOH solution and from the standard Beer's law plot. The stoichiometry thus determined was found to be 6 moles of Ce^{IV} to 1 mole of DAA. Thus, the overall stoichiometric equation could be written as

Results and Discussion

Ce^{IV} -DAA reaction in H_2SO_4 medium: Under the conditions $[DAA] \gg [Ce^{IV}]$, the order in $[Ce^{IV}]$ was found to be unity both in presence and absence of Ir^{III} as indicated by linear plots of $\log a/(a-x)$ vs time (Fig. 1A). From the slopes of these plots, the first order rate constants (k_{obs}) were evaluated. Increase in the concentration of DAA increased the rate and the order in [DAA] was found to be unity in the absence of Ir^{III} and fractional in the presence of Ir^{III} (Fig. 1B). The rate increased with increase in the concentration of Ir^{III} , and the order in the concentration of 5.0×10^{-6} to $1.62 \times 10^{-4} M$ of $[Ir^{III}]$ was found to be fractional (Fig. 3A, A'). The formation of free

radicals was identified by induced polymerisation of acrylonitrile. The rate increased with increase in $[H^+]$ at constant ionic strength but decreased at varying ionic strength both in catalysed and

Fig. 1. (A) $\log a/(a-x)$ vs time; $[Ce^{IV}] = 5.00 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[H_2SO_4] = 0.500 M$, $[DAA] = 5.00 \times 10^{-2} M$, $[Ir^{III}] = 5.00 \times 10^{-6} M$, Temp. = 303 K. (B) $\log$ rate vs $\log [DAA]$; $[DAA] = 2.50 \times 10^{-2}$ to $10.0 \times 10^{-2} M$, other conditions are same as in (A), and (C) $\log k_{obs}$ vs $1/T$.

uncatalysed reaction. The rate decreased with increase in $[HSO_4^-]$ or $[SO_4^{2-}]$ indicating neutral $Ce(SO_4)_3$ to be the reactive species⁴. The fractional order in $[DAA]$ in the presence of Ir^{III} indicates that the substrate is involved in complex formation either with Ce^{IV} or Ir^{III} . Our earlier work⁶ indicates that DAA in H_2SO_4 medium does not form kinetically detectable complexes with Ce^{IV} . Platinum group metal ions are well known to form complexes with organic substrates¹⁰. The λ_{max} of Ir^{III} solution was shifted to longer wavelength (435 nm) in the presence of DAA, indicating that there is some sort of interaction between DAA and Ir^{III} . Hence, the probable mechanism for the catalysed reaction could be written as

The rate law from the above mechanism could be written as

$$\frac{-d[Ce^{IV}]}{dt} = \frac{kK[Ce^{IV}][Ir^{III}][DAA]}{1 + K[Ir^{III}] + K[DAA]} \quad (1)$$

The above rate law explains the first order dependence of rate on $[Ce^{IV}]$ and fractional order dependence on $[substrate]$ and $[Ir^{III}]$. Equation (1) could also be written as

$$\frac{-2.303 d \log [Ce^{IV}]}{dt} = k_{obs} = \frac{kK[DAA][Ir^{III}]}{1 + K[DAA] + [Ir^{III}]} \quad (2)$$

By taking reciprocals of equation (2),

$$\frac{1}{k_{obs}} = \left[\frac{1}{kK[DAA][Ir^{III}]} + \frac{1}{k[DAA]} \right] + \frac{1}{k[Ir^{III}]} \quad (3)$$

from the intercept and slope of the line obtained by plotting $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[DAA]$, the rate constant (k) for the slow step and formation constant K were calculated.

Ce^{IV}-DAA reactions in HClO₄ medium: In the uncatalysed reaction, the order in $[Ce^{IV}]$ was one and that in $[DAA]$ fractional. The rate increased with increase in $[HClO_4]$ at constant ionic strength both in the presence and absence of Ir^{III} . Increase in $[ClO_4^-]$ increased the rate. The effects of $[HClO_4]$ and $[ClO_4^-]$ on rate were similar to those observed earlier⁴ and hence $[Ce(H_2O)_6]^{4+}$ is assumed to be reactive species in this case also. The uncatalysed reaction between Ce^{IV} and DAA in $HClO_4$ medium could be explained by a mechanism involving initial formation of a Ce^{IV} -DAA complex. The evidence for formation of such a complex between Ce^{IV} and DAA was obtained both from kinetic as well as spectrophotometric methods. The mechanism proposed is

The above mechanism gives a rate law,

$$\frac{-d[\text{Ce}^{IV}]}{dt} = \frac{kK[\text{Ce}^{IV}][\text{DAA}]}{1+K[\text{DAA}]} \quad (4)$$

which explains the first order dependence of rate on $[\text{Ce}^{IV}]$ and fractional order dependence on $[\text{DAA}]$. In the presence of Ir^{III} the rate law is similar except for the increase in rate constant. The order in $[\text{DAA}]$ was fractional and in $[\text{Ce}^{IV}]$ unity (Fig. 2A, B). The order of $[\text{Ir}^{III}]$ determined in the concentration range 2.0×10^{-6} to

Fig. 2. (A) $\log a/(a-x)$ vs time; $[\text{Ce}^{IV}] = 5.00 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[\text{DAA}] = 5.00 \times 10^{-2} M$, $[\text{HClO}_4] = 0.50 M$, $[\text{Ir}^{III}] = 2.50 \times 10^{-6} M$, Temp. = 303 K, (B) $\log$ rate vs $\log [\text{DAA}]$; $[\text{DAA}] = 2.50 \times 10^{-2}$ to $10 \times 10^{-2} M$, other conditions are same as (A), and (C) $\log k_{obs}$ vs $1/T$.

$5.00 \times 10^{-5} M$ was found to be fractional (0.65) (Fig. 3B, B'). Since catalysis is observed both in H_2SO_4 and HClO_4 media, it is not unreasonable to assume the first step to be formation of a $[\text{Ir}^{III}\text{-DAA}]$ complex as in H_2SO_4 . Kinetic and optical evidences indicate that a complex is also formed between Ce^{IV} and DAA in the presence

Fig. 3 (A) Plot of $[\text{Ir}^{III}]$ vs rate in H_2SO_4 medium; $[\text{Ir}^{III}] = 5.00 \times 10^{-6}$ to $1.62 \times 10^{-4} M$, (A') plot of $\log [\text{Ir}^{III}]$ vs $\log$ rate, (B) plot of $[\text{Ir}^{III}]$ vs rate in HClO_4 medium; $[\text{Ir}^{III}] = 2.50 \times 10^{-6}$ to $5.00 \times 10^{-5} M$, and (B') plot of $\log [\text{Ir}^{III}]$ vs $\log$ rate.

of Ir^{III} . Hence, the probable mechanism could be written as

The rate equation for the above scheme could be derived as

$$\frac{-d[\text{Ce}^{IV}]}{dt} = \frac{K_1 K_2 k_3 [\text{Ce}^{IV}][\text{DAA}][\text{Ir}^{III}]}{1 + [\text{DAA}]\{1 + K_2[\text{Ir}^{III}]\} + K_1 + K_2 + K_1 K_2[\text{Ir}^{III}] + K_1 K_2[\text{DAA}]} \quad (5)$$

or

$$\frac{-2.303 \, d \log [Ce^{IV}]}{dt} = k_0 b_3 = \frac{K_1 K_2 k_3 [DAA] [Ir^{III}]}{1/[DAA] \{1 + K_2 [Ir^{III}]\} + K_1 + K_2 + K_1 K_2 [Ir^{III}] + K_1 K_2 [DAA]} \quad (6)$$

The above equation accounts for the first order dependence on $[Ce^{IV}]$ and fractional order on $[Ir^{III}]$ and $[DAA]$. Owing to the complexity of equation (6), the rate constant for step 3 (k_3) and equilibrium constants (K_1, K_2) could not be determined as was done in H_2SO_4 medium. Though the rates are much slower in H_2SO_4 than $HClO_4$ under uncatalysed conditions, from the data in Table 1, it

TABLE 1—CATALYTIC COEFFICIENTS (k_{cat}/k_0) IN H_2SO_4 AND $HClO_4$ MEDIA AT VARYING $[Ir^{III}]$

$[Ce^{IV}] = 5.00 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[DAA] = 5.00 \times 10^{-2} M$,
 $[H^+] = 0.500 M$, Temp. = 303 K

$[Ir^{III}]$ $\times 10^5$ $mol^{-1} dm^{-3}$	$k_{H_2SO_4}$ $\times 10^4$ $dm^3 mol^{-2} s^{-1}$	k_{HClO_4} $\times 10^5$ $dm^3 mol^{-1} s^{-1}$	k_{cat}/k_0	
			H_2SO_4	$HClO_4$
0.00	0.383	1.02	—	—
0.50	7.68	11.7	20.1	11.6
1.05	11.7	11.4	30.5	13.6
1.40	14.5	15.7	37.8	15.4
1.75	18.4	17.5	47.5	17.1
2.00	20.8	19.9	54.0	19.5

is clear that catalysis is more pronounced in H_2SO_4 than $HClO_4$ medium. For instance, under similar conditions, the catalytic ratios (k_{cat}/k_0) are 20.1 and 11.6 in H_2SO_4 and $HClO_4$ media, respectively. This could be explained as follows. The oxidation potentials of Ce^{IV}/Ce^{III} couple in $HClO_4$ and H_2SO_4 are 1.6 and 1.4 V, respectively. Due to high potential of Ce^{IV}/Ce^{III} couple in $HClO_4$, the uncatalysed reaction itself is faster. Since perchlorate ions are poor ligands, they do not form complexes with Ce^{IV} and Ce^{IV} exists mainly as $Ce^{4+}(aq)$ at moderately high acid concentrations and low concentrations of Ce^{IV} used in the present work. In view of this, Ce^{IV} oxidises DAA via

formation of a complex and oxidation via inner-sphere mechanism is faster compared to outersphere mechanism that is operative in H_2SO_4 medium. In H_2SO_4 , SO_4^{2-} ions being better ligands, preferentially coordinate with $Ce^{4+}(aq)$ and form $Ce(SO_4)_2$ and this oxidises DAA by an outersphere mechanism. The rates of such reactions are obviously slow. In the presence of Ir^{III} , the mechanism envisages formation of a Ir^{III} -DAA complex which is oxidised by Ce^{IV} species. This Ce^{IV} species is $Ce(SO_4)_2$ in H_2SO_4 , while in $HClO_4$ medium it could be either free $Ce^{4+}(aq)$ or Ce^{4+} -DAA complex. In view of the high concentration of DAA used it is likely that all Ce^{4+} is present in the form of Ce^{4+} -DAA complex in $HClO_4$ medium. In H_2SO_4 , the mechanism envisages a reaction between (Ir^{III} -DAA) complex and $Ce(SO_4)_2$ in slow step, whereas in $HClO_4$ the slow step is the reaction between (Ir^{III} -DAA) and (Ce^{IV} -DAA) complexes. It is well known that complexation reduces the oxidation potential of metal ion considerably and probably with DAA also. The reduction in the potential appears to be high. Therefore, the reaction between (Ir^{III} -DAA) and $Ce(SO_4)_2$ is expected to be much faster than (Ir^{III} -DAA) and (Ce^{IV} -DAA) reaction in $HClO_4$. This accounts for the increased catalysis observed in H_2SO_4 .

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